

Supplementary Material for "When Corporate Chatbots Show Bias: A Multi-Dimensional Analysis of LLMs in Enterprise Settings"

Shreya Bhattacharya, Vincent Hagenow, Marco Di Gennaro

Abstract

This supplementary material provides additional experimental details and comprehensive data tables that support the findings presented in our primary manuscript, "When Corporate Chatbots Show Bias: A Multi-Dimensional Analysis of LLMs in Enterprise Settings." The tables included here offer a more granular view of the retrieval, grammar, and language bias experiments, including full contingency tables, statistical test results, and detailed per-model metrics. This data is provided to ensure full transparency and reproducibility of our research. The source code and raw data for all experiments are publicly available at [1] to facilitate further research.

1 Detailed Retrieval Bias Results

This section contains supplementary data for the retrieval bias experiments described in Section 4.1 of the main paper. The tables below provide a complete breakdown of the retrieval accuracy, agreement, and contingency data for each evaluated LLM, as well as the distributions for length-based and language-based biases.

Table 1: Retrieval Accuracy and Inter-Annotator Agreement Metrics. Accuracy measures the percentage of correct document rankings. Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Cohen’s Kappa quantify the average deviation and agreement with the ground truth, respectively.

Model	Accuracy (%)	MAE	Cohen’s Kappa
Claude	74.5	0.32	0.66
Cohere	51.5	0.68	0.35
GPT	40.0	1.00	0.20
Mistral	36.5	1.05	0.15
DeepSeek	35.0	1.07	0.13

Table 2: Grammatical Robustness Metrics. These metrics reflect each model’s ability to maintain high retrieval accuracy despite grammatical errors or stylistic variations in the prompt.

Model	Accuracy (%)	MAE	Cohen’s Kappa
Claude	76.92	0.23	0.54
Cohere	61.54	0.38	0.23
DeepSeek	61.54	0.38	0.23
Mistral	58.97	0.41	0.18
GPT	56.41	0.44	0.13

Table 3: Contingency Table of Correct vs. Incorrect Rankings by Model. This table shows the raw counts of correct and incorrect responses across all prompts for each evaluated LLM.

Model	Incorrect	Correct
Claude	18	60
Cohere	30	48
DeepSeek	30	48
GPT	34	44
Mistral	32	46

Table 4: Distribution Table for Length Bias. This table presents the raw counts of documents of different lengths (long, medium, short) that were ranked first, second, or third by each LLM, revealing any systematic preference for document length.

Model	Rank	long	medium	short
Claude	1	22	21	4
	2	11	22	14
	3	14	4	29
Cohere	1	22	18	7
	2	13	25	9
	3	12	4	31
DeepSeek	1	13	16	18
	2	13	23	11
	3	21	8	18
GPT	1	25	10	12
	2	12	28	7
	3	10	9	28
Mistral	1	14	16	17
	2	12	20	15
	3	21	11	15

Table 5: Contingency Tables for Language Bias per Rank. This table shows the raw counts for each language (de, en, fr, nl) that appeared at each ranking position (1-4) for each model, highlighting the models' language preferences.

Model	Rank	de	en	fr	nl
Claude	1	0	45	1	0
	2	2	8	26	10
	3	7	6	9	24
	4	31	5	4	6
Cohere	1	1	43	1	1
	2	6	8	21	11
	3	16	7	6	17
	4	17	7	12	10
DeepSeek	1	1	43	1	1
	2	2	9	25	10
	3	19	6	4	17
	4	18	7	9	12
GPT	1	7	30	4	5
	2	4	19	21	2
	3	11	8	11	16
	4	19	7	3	17
Mistral	1	1	42	2	1
	2	8	8	18	12
	3	18	7	7	14
	4	14	8	12	12

2 Detailed Statistical Analysis Results

This section provides the full results of the statistical tests performed to validate the observed trends in the main paper. Table 6 presents the pairwise comparison results for retrieval performance, and Table 7 shows the regression analysis results for reinforcement bias.

Table 6: Pairwise Comparison of Models (using Tukey’s HSD test). This table shows the mean difference (**meandiff**), adjusted p-value (**p-adj**), and 95% confidence interval (**lower** and **upper**) for each pairwise comparison. A value of **True** in the **reject** column indicates a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$) between the two models.

group1	group2	meandiff	p-adj	lower	upper	reject
Claude	Cohere	-0.0157	0.0195	-0.0298	-0.0017	True
Claude	Deepseek	0.0087	0.4346	-0.0053	0.0228	False
Claude	GPT	0.0211	0.0004	0.0070	0.0351	True
Claude	Mistral	0.0138	0.0574	-0.0003	0.0278	False
Cohere	Deepseek	0.0245	0.0000	0.0104	0.0385	True
Cohere	GPT	0.0368	0.0000	0.0227	0.0508	True
Cohere	Mistral	0.0295	0.0000	0.0154	0.0436	True
Deepseek	GPT	0.0123	0.1176	-0.0017	0.0264	False
Deepseek	Mistral	0.0050	0.8645	-0.0090	0.0191	False
GPT	Mistral	-0.0073	0.6194	-0.0213	0.0068	False

Table 7: Regression Analysis of Reinforcement Bias. This table shows the mean score and standard deviation for each model over 50 iterations, along with the p-value for the slope of a linear regression. A non-significant p-value (e.g., $p > 0.05$) for the slope indicates no statistically significant change (drift) in the model’s responses over repeated queries.

Model	Mean Score	Std Dev	Trend	p-value (slope)
Claude	4.60	0.55	No Change	0.86
GPT	4.25	0.79	No Change	0.27
Mistral	3.86	1.00	No Change	0.87
Cohere	3.48	1.07	No Change	0.37
DeepSeek	3.28	1.02	No Change	0.57

3 Detailed Language Bias Results

The tables in this section present additional data from the language bias experiments. Table 8 provides a summary of the Chi-Square test results for each LLM, indicating whether the same-language response rate differed significantly across prompt languages. Table 9 offers a granular breakdown of the responses

by prompt language and whether the generated output matched the input language.

Table 8: Overall Same-Language Response Rates and Chi-Square Test Results by LLM. The Chi-Square test was used to determine if there was a significant association between the prompt language and the likelihood of the LLM responding in the same language. The p-value for a significant difference is $p < 0.05$.

LLM	Total Answers	% Same Language	χ^2 Statistic	df	p-value	Significant?
Claude	67	83.75%	17.18	3	0.001	Yes
GPT	66	82.50%	7.27	3	0.064	No
Mistral	41	51.25%	36.17	3	0.001	Yes
Cohere	21	26.25%	75.09	3	0.001	Yes
Deepseek	77	96.25%	9.35	3	0.025	Yes

Table 9: Same-Language vs. Different-Language Responses by LLM and Prompt Language. This contingency table provides the raw counts for same-language and different-language responses for each LLM and for each of the four evaluated languages (German, English, French, and Dutch).

LLM	Prompt Language	Same Language	Different Language	Total Prompts
Claude	German (de)	12	8	20
	English (en)	20	0	20
	French (fr)	20	0	20
	Dutch (nl)	15	5	20
GPT	German (de)	14	6	20
	English (en)	20	0	20
	French (fr)	17	3	20
	Dutch (nl)	15	5	20
Mistral	German (de)	4	16	20
	English (en)	20	0	20
	French (fr)	13	7	20
	Dutch (nl)	4	16	20
Cohere	German (de)	0	20	20
	English (en)	20	0	20
	French (fr)	1	19	20
	Dutch (nl)	0	20	20
Deepseek	German (de)	20	0	20
	English (en)	20	0	20
	French (fr)	20	0	20
	Dutch (nl)	17	3	20

References

- [1] Source code and raw data for all experiments are publicly available at <https://github.com/UnBiasAI>.